

Title: The impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the care of dermatology inpatients – our experience in a tertiary hospital in Singapore

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Introduction: The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly altered the landscape of healthcare delivery to patients globally. Our dermatology ward, sited in the National Centre of Infectious Diseases, is the dedicated institution critically involved in the fight against the pandemic. Consequently, our dermatology inpatients were decanted and relocated to various wards at an adjacent hospital, without access to our team of specialty trained nurses. We were concerned about the resultant impact this would have on patients' hospitalisation outcomes. In anticipation of this, we conducted training for these nurses across different wards in dermatological nursing for common disorders encountered.

Objectives: This study aims to determine the effects of decentralised non-specialised nursing care on patient outcomes and to evaluate if dermatology nursing specific training mitigated any deleterious fallout. The primary outcomes are the length of hospitalization and rate of unplanned readmissions of dermatology in-patients. Secondary outcomes include complications of prolonged hospitalization such as nosocomial infections, urinary retention, delirium, and functional decline.

Materials and Method: A retrospective review of case notes of all dermatology in-patients admitted with common dermatological diagnoses during the period of 1 March 2020 to 31 December 2020 was performed. This was compared to a similar population of in-patients who were admitted during the pre-pandemic period of 1 March 2019 to 31 December 2019.

Results: A total of 484 admissions were included, of which 311 admissions were during the pre-pandemic period while 173 admissions were during the COVID-19 pandemic. The median length of hospitalization for patients admitted during the pandemic (6 days, interquartile range 4 to 9 days) was longer compared to the pre-pandemic period (5 days, interquartile range 3 to 8 days), but was not found to be statistically significant ($p=0.283$). Unplanned readmission rate was 8.86% during the pandemic and 11.55% pre-pandemic, but the difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.421$). For our secondary outcomes, we

found that there was a significantly higher incidence of thrombophlebitis (5.78%) in patients admitted during the pandemic period compared to the pre-pandemic period (1.29%). Other secondary outcomes did not differ significantly between the groups.

Conclusion: Early interventions of rendering dermatology specific training to non-specialist nurses helped to mitigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the care of our in-patients.